

1 **Behavior of coastal amagmatic geothermal systems: Insights from the La Jolla beach,**
2 **Baja California, Mexico**

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11
12 **Abstract**

13 The coastal amagmatic orogenic geothermal system in La Jolla Beach, Baja California, Mexico,
14 holds significant potential as a geothermal resource for electricity generation and seawater
15 desalination. This study investigates the influence of topography, bathymetry, and sediments on
16 the regional water circulation within the crystalline basement and the Agua Blanca Fault, providing
17 insights into the behavior of coastal geothermal systems. Three-dimensional thermal–hydraulic
18 simulations are conducted, considering fault widths, permeability values, and the topography of
19 the crystalline basement. The results highlight the critical role of fault permeability in facilitating
20 the infiltration of meteoric and seawater, leading to the formation of thermal water upflow zones.
21 Simulated surface thermal anomalies (>90 °C) are observed when fault permeability exceeds 10⁻¹⁴
22 m². Infiltration of water in the host rock accounts for less than 25%, with most occurring along
23 the fault zone. The interplay of hydraulic heads, seawater density, and sediments influences flow
24 direction, controlling the location of coastal thermal anomalies and restricting the movement of
25 meteoric water beyond the coastline. Fault width does not determine the position of the anomaly
26 but does impact the water and heat flux, which correlate with low fluid pressure zones. Simulations
27 successfully reproduce the surface temperature (~94 °C), location, extent, and seawater fractions
28 (<35%) of the La Jolla Beach geothermal system. This study provides insights into the behavior
29 of coastal geothermal systems, emphasizing the role of topography, bathymetry, salinity,

30 sediments, and fault permeability in determining the temperature and location of coastal
31 geothermal systems. Our findings contribute to a better understanding of similar systems globally.

32

33 **1 Introduction**

34 Coastal amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems represent a distinct subtype within the
35 amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems, characterized by their remarkable thermal phenomena.
36 These systems exhibit a notable feature known as the diffusive discharge of thermal water onto
37 the sandy beaches and rocks during the low tide, extending up to a hundred meters within the
38 intertidal zone (Lynn, 1978). These systems exhibit thermal water discharge with temperatures
39 varying from 30 to 100 °C, along with lower salinity and pH compared to seawater (Carbajal-
40 Martínez et al., 2020). Understanding the mechanisms behind this thermal water discharge and its
41 implications is vital for unlocking the potential of these geothermal systems and harnessing their
42 energy resources, such as in seawater desalination processes (Karytsas et al., 2002).

43 Amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems originate in areas that lack recent magmatic
44 activity where meteoric water is driven by mountains and infiltrates through interconnected
45 fractures, circulating at great depth along permeable fault zones. As the water flows through the
46 rock, it acquires heat from the surrounding wall rocks, then rises and discharges into valley floors
47 along the fault (López & Smith, 1995; Coussens et al., 2018; Diamond et al., 2018; Alt-Epping et
48 al., 2022). These fault-hosted systems are characterized by average geothermal gradient less than
49 30 °C km⁻¹, reservoir temperatures reaching up to 250 °C, and spring temperatures of from 25 to
50 99 °C. The behavior and characteristics of amagmatic geothermal systems, including water upflow
51 rates, discharge temperatures, water equilibration depth, water residence times, and the magnitude
52 and location of thermal anomalies, are influenced by two crucial factors: the variability of the
53 hydraulic head gradient and the permeability of faults (Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2023). While the
54 main processes governing the behavior of amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems are reasonably
55 well understood, their coastal counterparts present intriguing knowledge gaps, particularly
56 regarding the processes associated with seawater circulation.

57 Coastal geothermal systems with thermal water occurrences along the shoreline are
58 observed in various locations worldwide. Notable examples include Hot Water Beach in New
59 Zealand (50 °C, Lyon & Giggenbach, 1992), the Akropotamos coastal zone in Greece (46 °C,
60 Papachristou et al., 2021), and the Gölbası coastal spring in Turkey (30 °C, Gökğöz & Akdağoğlu,

61 2016). Along the Baja California Peninsula in Mexico, at least 12 coastal geothermal systems have
62 been documented, as depicted in Figure 1 (López-Sánchez et al., 2006; Camprubí et al., 2008;
63 Hernández-Morales & Wurl, 2017; Batista Cruz et al., 2019; Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2020;
64 Hernández-Morales et al., 2021). These systems are linked to regional faults that act as permeable
65 channels for deep water circulation and the exfiltration of thermal water in the coastal zones at
66 temperatures between 30 to 94 °C. Detailed insights into the circulation and mixing processes of
67 meteoric and seawater through permeable faults running parallel to the coast have been obtained
68 through two-dimensional numerical simulations conducted in Seferihisar, Turkey, and the Dead
69 Sea in Israel. These simulations have revealed the occurrence of deep-water circulation at the
70 intersections of faults within the basement, with seawater traveling several kilometers along the
71 basement interface before ascending back to the shore as thermal saline water (Shalev & Yechieli,
72 2007; Magri et al., 2012).

73 Unexplained phenomena persist regarding coastal amagmatic orogenic geothermal
74 systems, specifically the systematic occurrences of multiple thermal anomalies in coastal zones
75 and the three-dimensional underlying processes governing their magnitude. Understanding these
76 phenomena is crucial for enhancing exploration and heat extraction strategies for these geothermal
77 reservoirs. Therefore, in this study, we conducted 3D thermal–hydraulic numerical simulations of
78 the amagmatic coastal geothermal system at La Jolla beach in Ensenada, Baja California, Mexico.
79 La Jolla Beach was selected for several reasons: firstly, it is recognized as the hottest coastal
80 amagmatic geothermal system worldwide, according to our knowledge. Secondly, extensive data
81 regarding its location, size, and shallow temperature have been recorded (Carbajal-Martínez et al.,
82 2020). Lastly, a well-established geothermal conceptual model exists for this site (Carbajal-
83 Martínez et al., 2023). Additionally, crucial input data from the Pacific Ocean were incorporated,
84 including seafloor bathymetry (NOAA National Geophysical Data Center, 2006), seawater
85 temperature (Emery & Dewar, 1982), seafloor sediment distribution (Emery, et al., 1957), and the
86 topography of the crystalline basement (Pérez-Flores et al., 2004), to facilitate the performance
87 of our simulations.

88 In this study, we capitalize on these features to evaluate the role of topography, bathymetry,
89 and sediments in investigating the three-dimensional regional seawater and meteoric water
90 circulation within the crystalline basement and faults, aiming to gain insights into the behavior,
91 location, and magnitude of coastal amagmatic orogenic geothermal systems. Our approach

92 encompasses large-scale 3D thermal–hydraulic numerical simulations that incorporate varying
93 fault widths and permeability values. Through this methodology, we provide valuable insights into
94 the processes that govern the occurrence of coastal amagmatic geothermal systems, thereby aiding
95 in the future management and utilization of geothermal resources.

96 1.1 Features of the study area

97 This study focuses on investigating La Jolla Beach, the hottest coastal geothermal system
98 located in the northwest of the Baja California Peninsula (Figure 1a). The geothermal system is
99 hosted in the western section of the Agua Blanca Fault (ABF), which exhibits the highest degree
100 of extension along its 150 km length (Wetmore et al., 2019). This extension is indicative of the
101 most permeable zone within the fault system. The ABF is a subvertical west–northwest-trending
102 (276–302°) dextral–normal structure that was first active between 3.3 and 1.5 Ma (Wetmore et al.,
103 2019). In the western portion, the ABF splits into two dextral branches that encircle the Punta
104 Banda Peninsula (Figure 1b). This tectonic activity has contributed to the formation of 12 marine
105 terraces since 1.3 Ma (Rockwell et al., 1989) and the formation of an extensional sedimentary
106 basin in Bahía Todos Santos and Maneadero (Figure 1b) (Pérez-Flores et al., 2004). This activity
107 has also resulted in the development of two other geothermal systems in the southern branch of
108 the ABF, El Retiro beach (35 °C) and a submarine fumarolic field (102°C, Vidal et al., 1978).

109 The thermal water discharged at La Jolla beach is mixed with seawater and has a slightly
110 acidic pH (~7) and lower salinity (8.5–16 g L⁻¹) than the local seawater (34.0 g L⁻¹). The thermal
111 anomaly at La Jolla becomes visible during low tide periods and extends approximately 300 m in
112 length and 100 m in width. Temperatures within the anomaly range from 20 to 94 °C (Figure 1c)
113 (Carbajal-Martínez et al., 2020). In the vicinity of the anomaly, six shallow thermal wells exhibit
114 temperatures ranging from 29 to 73 °C. Furthermore, four electrical resistivity tomography
115 sections (up to 80 m depth, Figure 1d) indicate the presence of a conductive anomaly (0.8 Ω m)
116 beneath the coastal thermal anomaly, suggesting the presence of thermal and saline water in the
117 subsurface 500 m around La Jolla beach (Arango-Galván et al., 2011; Carbajal-Martínez, 2019).

118 The geothermal system at La Jolla is characterized by an amagmatic origin with a mantle
119 contribution of less than 3%, as indicated by helium isotopes and gases analysis. The recharge of
120 this geothermal system occurs mainly through meteoric water at an elevation 770 m a.s.l. in the
121 mountainous zone, as indicated by stable isotopes of water. The solutes concentration suggests that

122 the water–rock equilibrium is reached at a depth of ~6 km with a temperature of 160 °C (Carbajal-
123 [Martinez et al., 2023](#)).

124 The numerical simulations conducted in this study expand upon the conceptual model
125 proposed by [Carbajal-Martinez et al. \(2023\)](#), which highlights the importance of hydraulic head
126 gradients and fault permeability in governing the behavior of amagmatic geothermal systems.
127 According to this conceptual model, meteoric water infiltrates from higher altitudes into the
128 basement, where it undergoes heating due to a geothermal gradient of 24 °C km⁻¹. High
129 permeability and hydraulic head gradients lead to deep-water penetration, resulting in resulting in
130 a deep water-rock equilibration temperatures and rapid thermal water upflow velocities. The
131 chemical composition of the infiltrated meteoric water changes along its flow path, influenced by
132 water residence times and mixing processes with ancient seawater-like porewater as well as
133 mineral precipitation and dissolution and mixing with fresh seawater. As a result, the salty thermal
134 water discharged into the coastal zone can reach temperatures as high as 94 °C.

135 By combining numerical simulations with the conceptual model, this study provides further
136 insights into the mechanisms governing the three-dimensional behavior of coastal amagmatic
137 geothermal system.

Figure 1. Location, Structural Setting, and Geothermal Features of the Study Area. a) Location of Coastal Geothermal Systems along the Baja California Peninsula in Mexico (Yellow Stars). b) Structural Setting, Marine Terraces, and Location of Amagmatic Geothermal Systems in Punta Banda Peninsula, Baja California, Mexico. The Peninsula is surrounded by two dextral branches of the ABF. c) Location of the Coastal Geothermal Systems at La Jolla Beach. The figure shows the thermal anomaly present at the beach, as well as the positions of six shallow domestic wells (indicated by yellow markers) and four electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) profiles (marked by black lines P1 to P4). The temperature values of the coastal thermal anomaly represent measurements taken at a depth of 20 cm below the beach surface. d) Electrical Resistivity Tomography Sections for the Four Profiles corresponding to the black lines P1 to P4 shown in Figure 1c (after [Arango-Galván et al., 2011](#); [Carbajal-Martinez, 2019](#)). Blue color indicates a low resistivity value of rocks. The vertical black lines in sections P3 and P4 illustrate the location and depth of two thermal domestic wells.

139 2 Numerical simulations methodology

140 The forward-coupled thermal-hydraulic numerical simulations in this study were
 141 performed using the TOUGH code, an integral finite difference model known for its capability to
 142 simulate water transport in liquid, vapor, and two-phase states (Pruess et al., 1999). The TOUGH
 143 code incorporates temperature-dependent properties of water, including viscosity, density, and
 144 enthalpy, utilizing steam table equations provided by the International Formulation Committee
 145 (1967). TOUGH solves the partial differential equations governing mass balance and heat flow by
 146 employing Newton–Raphson iterations.

$$\frac{\partial M^{W,H}}{\partial t} = -\text{div}\mathbf{F}^{W,H} + q^{L,H} \quad (1)$$

147 where $M^{W,H}$ is the total mass accumulation term of water (W) and heat (H) in the system. $F^{W,H}$ is
 148 the total mass flux rate for water ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and heat ($\text{J m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), and $q^{W,H}$ is the sink ($-$) or source
 149 ($+$) term for each component. The equation essentially balances the inflows and outflows of water
 150 and heat in a given system, taking into account any sources or sinks.

151 The general form of water accumulation term in equation 1 can be written as

$$M^W = \phi \sum_{\beta} S_{\beta} \rho_{\beta} X_{\beta}^W \quad (2)$$

152 the total mass of component M^W (kg m^{-3}) per unit volumen is obtained by summing over the fluid
 153 phases β (liquid, gas, non-aqueous phase liquid) and by the product of porosity (ϕ), the saturation
 154 of phase (S_{β}) that is the fraction of pore volume occupied by β , the density of phase is ρ_{β} , and
 155 X_{β}^W is the mass fraction of component W present in phase β .

156 The advective flux of a component (\mathbf{F}_{adv}^W) in mass balance equation 1 is a sum over phases:

$$\mathbf{F}_{adv}^W = \sum_{\beta} X_{\beta}^W \mathbf{F}_{\beta} \quad (3)$$

157 Individual phase fluxes in equation 3 are calculated using a multiphase version of Darcy Law

$$\mathbf{F}_{\beta} = \rho_{\beta} \mathbf{u}_{\beta} = -k \frac{k_{r\beta} \rho_{\beta}}{\mu_{\beta}} (\nabla P_{\beta} - \rho_{\beta} \mathbf{g}) \quad (4)$$

158 where \mathbf{u}_{β} is the Darcy velocity (flux volume) in phase β (m s^{-1}). The absolute permeability is
 159 represented by k (m^2), and the relative permeability to the phase is $k_{r\beta}$ (m^2). Viscosity is
 160 represented by μ_{β} (Pa s), and P_{β} is the fluid pressure in phase β (Pa m^{-1}) and \mathbf{g} is the vector of
 161 gravitational acceleration (m s^{-2}).

162 In the same way, the general form of heat accumulation term (J m^{-3}) in equation 1 is:

$$M^H = (1 - \phi)\rho_R C_R T + \phi \sum_{\beta} S_{\beta} \rho_{\beta} u_{\beta} \quad (5)$$

163 where C_R ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) and ρ_R (kg m^{-3}) are the specific heat capacity and the density of the porous
 164 medium (rock + porewater), T (K) is the temperature of the porous medium, u_{β} is the specific
 165 internal energy in phase β (J kg^{-1}).

166 Heat flux includes both conductive and convective heat components in the porous media

$$\mathbf{F}^H = -\lambda \nabla T + \sum_{\beta} \mathbf{F}_{\beta} h_{\beta} \quad (6)$$

167 where λ is thermal conductivity ($\text{J s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1} = \text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), h_{β} is the specific enthalpy in phase
 168 β (J kg^{-1}), and ∇T (K m^{-1}) is the gradient in temperature between adjacent grid blocks.

169 In order to accurately model the mixing of meteoric water and seawater, all simulations in
 170 this study utilized the EOS7 equation of state. This equation of state represents the aqueous phase
 171 as a combination of pure water and brine. The salinity of the mixture is represented by the brine
 172 fraction (X_b) which is assigned a value of one for seawater. The fluid density (ρ) and viscosity (μ)
 173 are calculated by interpolating between the values of pure water (ρ_w) and brine (ρ_b). The mixture
 174 density (ρ_m) can then be expressed in terms of water and brine densities as follows.

$$1/(\rho_m) = (1 - X_b)/(\rho_w) + (X_b/\rho_b) \quad (7)$$

175 To maintain consistency across all simulations, the density of the brine was set as to density
 176 of seawater 1025 kg m^{-3} at $20 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 10^5 Pa . On the other hand, salinity effects on aqueous phase
 177 viscosity are modeled with a polynomial correction to the viscosity of pure water. The mixture
 178 viscosity (μ_m) is represented as follows:

$$\mu_m(P, T, X_b) = \mu_m(P, T) f(X_b) \quad (8)$$

179 where

$$f(X_b) = 1 + v_1 X_b + v_2 X_b^2 + v_3 X_b^3 \quad (9)$$

180 with values of $v_1 = 0.066$, $v_2 = 0$, and $v_3 = 0$

181 The accuracy and reliability of the TOUGH code in modeling seawater-water mixing have
 182 been assessed by [Na et al. \(2019\)](#) through a comparison of laboratory experiments and numerical
 183 simulations. In our study, we also employed the EOS7 equation of state, incorporating the
 184 appropriate density and viscosity calculations to accurately capture the behavior of the mixed
 185 meteoric water and seawater in our simulations.

186 2.1 Model Geometry

187 Our numerical model encompasses a large 3D domain measuring $34 \times 12 \times 11.5$ km
188 (Figure 2). To accurately represent the study area, we discretized the model using an initially
189 regular rectangular mesh consisting of approximately 400,000 grid blocks. The grid block sizes
190 vary throughout the domain, with the highest resolution concentrated in the La Jolla beach area
191 ($15 \times 15 \times 20$ m). Figure 2 illustrates the variability of block sizes in the X and Y directions.

192 To account for the topography (up to 1 km) and bathymetry (up to 0.4 km) of the study
193 area, we incorporated a digital elevation model (DEM) obtained from the National Oceanic and
194 Atmospheric Administration ([NOAA National Geophysical Data Center, 2006](#)). The DEM served
195 as the basis for shaping the surface of the initial regular mesh using the "fit surface" method
196 available in the PyTOUGH software ([Croucher, 2015](#)). This process resulted in a 3D irregular
197 mesh that accurately represents the topography of the Punta Banda Peninsula and the seafloor
198 bathymetry (Figure 2).

199 2.2 Initial and boundary conditions

200 The simulations were initiated by setting initial Dirichlet conditions for hydrostatic
201 pressure and conductive temperature distributions. At the upper boundary, a fixed temperature was
202 assigned based on an ambient temperature of 16 °C at the coast ([CICESE, 2019](#)). The temperature
203 was further adjusted considering an adiabatic cooling rate of -5.5 °C km^{-1} over the continent and
204 a cooling gradient of -3.1 °C per 100 m depth in the seawater column ([Emery & Dewar, 1982](#)).

205 To define the inland continental pressure at the upper boundary, we utilized Equation 10
206 ([Cavcar, 2000](#)), which takes into account the altitude (z):

$$P_{continent} = 10^5 \times [1 - (0.0065 \times z / 289.15)]^{5.2561} \quad (10)$$

207 On other hand, the pressure on the seafloor boundary was determined based on the length
208 of the seawater column (h), the seawater density ($\rho_{sea} = 1025$ kg m^{-3}), and the acceleration due to
209 gravity (g ; m s^{-2}):

$$P_{seafloor} = \rho_{sea} \times g \times h \quad (11)$$

210 Assuming an initial conductive temperature distribution, the temperature increased with
211 depth according to the regional geothermal gradient of 24 °C km^{-1} ([Carbajal-Martinez, 2023](#)). The
212 temperature at the lower boundary (11 km below sea level) was fixed at 300 °C, considering the
213 geothermal gradient, the mean altitude of the surface topography (0.295 km), and the mean annual
214 temperature at sea level (16 °C). For the model boundaries, four lateral and lower boundaries were

215 open for conductive heat exchange and closed for fluid flow. The upper boundary, on the other
216 hand, was open for both heat and fluid flow, allowing for exchanges with the surroundings. These
217 boundary conditions ensure the appropriate representation of heat and fluid dynamics within the
218 numerical model, capturing the essential processes occurring in the La Jolla geothermal system.

219 2.3 Model parameters

220 The model was divided into three distinct domains: the host rock, fault zone, and brittle–
221 ductile transition (BDTZ). Since hydraulic well test measurements specific to the study area were
222 not available, permeability values for the host rock and fault were adopted from relevant studies
223 conducted in similar geological and tectonic settings (Stober & Bucher, 2007; Wanner et al., 2019;
224 Alt-Epping et al., 2021). The configuration of the host rock in the model accounted for depth-
225 dependent porosity (0.02 to 0.01) and permeability (Stober & Bucher, 2007). A fixed permeability
226 value of 10^{-16} m² was applied within the upper 2.5 km of the crust, and below that depth,
227 permeability was determined using Equation 12, which is based on hydraulic deep well
228 measurements worldwide, showing significant variations in permeability within the upper 2.5 km
229 of the crust.

$$\log k(\text{m}^2) = -1.38 \times \log (z) - 15.4 \quad (12)$$

230 The BDTZ located at the model base, was characterized by low permeability low
231 permeability (10^{-25} m²) and porosity (0.01) values. The fault zone was modeled without depth
232 dependence of permeability and porosity, and three different fault widths were simulated: 15 m,
233 45 m, and 105 m. The model assumed a homogeneous distribution of bulk rock density, thermal
234 conductivity, and specific heat capacity, as presented in Table

235

Figure 2. Large-scale model ($34 \times 12 \times 11.5$ km) of La Jolla Beach in Punta Banda, Baja California, Mexico. The figure depicts the surface topography and bathymetry of the study area, including the ABF and the BDTZ. Refer to the accompanying text for detailed information on the hydraulic and thermal properties as well as the boundary conditions applied within the model domain.

236

237 2.4 Numerical simulation Cases I, II, and III

238 To investigate the factors influencing the formation and location of coastal amagmatic
 239 geothermal systems, we conducted three distinct numerical simulation scenarios (Cases I, II, and
 240 III), as outlined in Table 1 and depicted in Figure 3. While we utilized the parameters described in
 241 subsection 2.3, several modifications were incorporated for each case.

242 In Case I, we assumed a homogeneous permeability and porosity within the fault plane without
 243 considering any sediment layers in the simulation (Figure 3a). For Case II, we introduced a seafloor
 244 sediment layer with a thickness of 50 m and a permeability of 10^{-18} m². Additionally, we considered
 245 the ABF traversing a seafloor sediment layer with a permeability of 10^{-16} m² (Figure 3b). In Case
 246 III, we integrated the basin configuration of Bahia Todos Santos and Maneadero, incorporating the
 247 lateral and depth distribution of sediments (sand and sill). To establish the depth of the crystalline
 248 basement, we employed the results from the joint inversion of gravity and magnetic data (Figure
 249 4c,b; Pérez-Flores et al., 2004). Furthermore, we utilized seafloor sediment samples collected from

250 the Pacific Ocean (Emery et al., 1957), as well as the lithological information derived from shallow
251 wells and geophysical measurements in Maneadero (Cruz Falcón & Vázquez González, 1989;
252 Daesslé et al., 2009). Permeability values for the sediments in Case III were based on reported
253 ranges (Luijendijk & Gleeson, 2017; Table 1). We assumed that the permeability of the fault within
254 the sediments was around one order higher compared to the surrounding sediments of the ABF
255 (Table 1). Additionally, a homogeneous thermal conductivity ($1.50 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and specific heat
256 capacity ($800 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) were assumed for the sediments in both Case II and Case III (Midttømme
257 et al., 1998).

258 It is important to note that the distinction between Case II and Case III lies in the specific
259 geological settings they represent. While Case II is designed as a synthetic simulation to gain
260 insights into the general behavior of coastal geothermal systems incorporating a thin layer of
261 sediment, Case III focuses on capturing the sedimentary and structural conditions unique to La
262 Jolla beach. Case III provides a more detailed and site-specific representation of the geothermal
263 system under investigation. This allows for a comprehensive understanding of the localized
264 dynamics and processes influencing the formation and behavior of the coastal magmatic
265 geothermal system in the La Jolla area.

Figure 3. Fault and sediment configuration and permeability values from different numerical simulations. The figure illustrates the fault and sediment configuration in three different cases of the numerical simulations. a) Case I: Homogeneous fault permeability. b) Case II: Thin seafloor sediment layer. c) Case III: Sedimentary basin. d) Section of Case III showcasing the basement topography and sediments along the ABF. Each case presents the permeability values of the fault, which correspond to the temperature of La Jolla Beach ($\sim 100^\circ C$), as well as the permeability of the onshore and offshore sediments. Additionally, the figure displays the permeability values of the sediments intersected by the ABF.

Table 1.

Description of the model dimension, boundary conditions, and hydraulic and thermal parameters for the numerical simulations (Cases I, II, II) of La Jolla beach, Baja California, Mexico. These parameters reproduce a thermal anomaly around 100 °C.

Parameters and description	Model and host rock	Fault width			Reference
		15 (m)	45 (m)	105 (m)	
<i>Dimension of model</i>					
N-W and S-E	34 × 12 km				(NOAA National Geophysical Data Center, 2006)
Base of model	-11.5 km				
Upper Boundary	Topography and bathymetry				
<i>Boundaries conditions</i>					
Continental upper pressure	Equation 10				(Cavcar, 2000)
Seafloor pressure	Equation 11				(Emery & Dewar, 1982)
Seawater density at 20 °C	1025 kg m ⁻³				
Gradient temperature of continental surface	-5.5 °C km ⁻¹				
Gradient temperature of seafloor					
Geothermal gradient	-3.1 °C 0.1 km ⁻¹				
Fixed <i>T</i> at the lower boundary	24 °C km ⁻¹				(Carbajal et al., 2023)
Permeability at the four laterals and lower boundaries	300 °C 10 ⁻²⁵ m ²				
<i>Hydraulic properties host rock</i>					
Vertical permeability	Equation 12 First 2.5 km fix at 10 ⁻¹⁶ m ²				(Stober & Bucher, 2007)
Porosity (linear decrease)	From 0.02 to 0.01				(Wanner et al., 2019)
Rock density	2680 kg m ⁻³				
<i>Fault hydraulic properties simulation Case I</i>					
Permeability					
Porosity		9.0 ⁻¹⁴ m ² 0.02	3.0 ⁻¹⁴ m ² 0.02	1.5 ⁻¹⁴ m ² 0.02	Sensitivity analysis
<i>Fault and sediment hydraulic properties simulation Case II</i>					
Permeability:					
Seafloor sediments	10 ⁻¹⁸ m ²				Sensitivity analysis
Sediments within the fault		4.5 ⁻¹⁵ m ²	2.9 ⁻¹⁵ m ²	9.0 ⁻¹⁶ m ²	
Fault (beneath sediments)		7.5 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	2.5 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	1.3 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	
Sediment porosity	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	(Luijendijk & Gleeson, 2017)
Rock density	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	
Sediment thickness	50 m	50 m	50 m	50 m	
<i>Fault and sediment hydraulic properties simulation Case III</i>					
Basin sediments permeability:					
Coarse sand	10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²				(Emery et al., 1957)
Medium sand	10 ⁻¹⁵ m ²				(Luijendijk & Gleeson, 2017)
Very fine sand	10 ⁻¹⁵ m ²				
Coarse silt	10 ⁻¹⁶ m ²				
Sediment permeability within the fault					
Coarse sand		10 ⁻¹³ m ²	10 ⁻¹³ m ²	10 ⁻¹³ m ²	Sensitivity analysis
Medium sand		10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	
Very fine sand		10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	
Coarse silt		10 ⁻¹⁵ m ²	3 × 10 ⁻¹⁶ m ²	3 × 10 ⁻¹⁶ m ²	
Fault (beneath sediments)		6.5 × 10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	2 × 10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	1.1 × 10 ⁻¹⁴ m ²	
Sediment porosity	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	(Luijendijk & Gleeson, 2017)
Rock density	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	2680 kg m ⁻³	
Sediment thickness	variable <1.5 km	variable <1.5 km	variable <1.5 km	variable <1.5 km	(Pérez-Flores et al., 2004)
<i>Thermal properties</i>					
Thermal conductivity host rock	3.34 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹				(Wanner et al., 2019)
Specific heat capacity host rock	920 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹				
Thermal conductivity sediments	1.50 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	1.50 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	1.50 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	1.50 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	(Midttømme et al., 1998)
Specific heat capacity sediments	800 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	800 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	800 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	800 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	

266

267 **3 Results and discussion**

268 3.1 Case I: homogenous fault permeability

269 We present 3D hydraulic-thermal simulation results in Figure 4 along the ABF that
270 includes the Pacific Ocean on the left (0–12 km) and the mountainous zone on the right, with La
271 Jolla beach approximately at 12 km (dotted black vertical line) (Figure 4a). Our sensitivity analysis
272 identified a narrow range of permeability values (e.g., fault width 15 m and $k = 5 \times 10^{-14}$ and $9 \times$
273 10^{-14} m^2) capable of generating a thermal anomaly on the surface, with temperatures ranging from
274 about 30 to 100 °C (Figure 4b). A fault width of 15 m and a permeability of $9 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$ result in
275 a surface temperature of $\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$, with pore water flux reaching up to $3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. However,
276 lower permeability values (below $5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$) do not produce any thermal anomaly due to the
277 low pore water flux ($< 4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) that could not transport heat from the host rock to the surface
278 (Figure 5).

279 Our study shows that the fault permeability significantly influences the extent of seawater
280 infiltration into the continent. As the fault permeability increases, the fraction of seawater
281 infiltration also increases (Figure 5) this effect was also observed by Karasaki et al. (2011) and
282 Magri et al. (2012). Seawater penetrates up to 4 km inland through the ABF. The fractions of
283 seawater in the thermal water discharged on the surface range from 10 to 70%. The fault
284 permeability also plays a crucial role in shaping the marine intrusion. When the permeability is
285 low, the marine intrusion has a gentle slope ($< 45^\circ$). However, as the permeability increases the
286 water flux is faster, then the intrusion takes on a semi-vertical plane ($\sim 80\text{--}90^\circ$), effectively acting
287 as a barrier to the circulation of meteoric water (Figure 5).

288 Our study highlights the critical role of fault permeability in facilitating the deep infiltration
289 of meteoric and seawater into the surrounding rock, ultimately leading to a thermal water upflow
290 zone. The high fault permeability promotes greater water velocity, leading to more efficient
291 interaction with the surrounding rock and acquiring heat. This process is driven by hydraulic head
292 gradients from the mountainous area and the Pacific Ocean, which ultimately result in the high
293 temperatures observed in our study (Figure 4d). However, while Case I can successfully replicate
294 the temperature of La Jolla beach, it fails to reproduce the location of the observed thermal
295 anomaly in the coastal zone. The thermal anomaly is situated 3–5 km inland from the coastline
296 (Figure 4b), primarily caused by the high permeability of the fault.

297 To replicate the temperature and position of the thermal anomaly at La Jolla beach, we
298 conducted additional simulations by increasing the fault width to 45 and 105 m and the
299 permeability to 3×10^{-14} and $1.5 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2$, respectively. These values resulted in a surface
300 temperature of approximately 100 °C with pore water fluxes ranging from 6×10^{-6} and 10^{-5} m s^{-1} .
301 Interestingly, we found that as the fault width increased, a lower permeability was required to
302 reproduce the thermal anomaly, resulting in a decrease in water flux. However, fault width had a
303 negligible effect on controlling the position of the thermal anomaly at the surface, which remained
304 between 3–5 km inland. The length of the thermal anomaly along the ABF also remained the same,
305 approximately 3 km (Figure 4e). These findings indicate that the high permeability of the ABF
306 enables seawater to circulate through it, with the density and hydraulic gradient of seawater
307 functioning as barriers that inhibit the circulation of meteoric water beyond the coastline. This
308 highlights the importance of seawater density in controlling the location of coastal thermal
309 anomalies. Our study also found that the resulting mix density of thermal water was approximately
310 960 kg m^{-3} , as both seawater and meteoric water experience a decrease in density when heated.
311 (Figure 4f).

312 It is important to note that accurately replicating the location of the thermal anomaly at the
313 coastal zone requires addressing the issue of seawater infiltration into the ABF. As such, it is
314 necessary to explore potential solutions for reducing the amount of seawater that infiltrates the
315 ABF, which will ultimately impact the thermal anomaly location. This will be discussed in detail
316 in the following subchapter.

Figure 4. Hydraulic–thermal numerical simulations analysis from Case I. a) (a) Topography and bathymetry section along the ABF, with La Jolla beach indicated by a dotted vertical line (~ at 12 km) on the fault profile. b) Sensitivity analysis for a 15 m wide fault to replicate the surface temperature of La Jolla at different fault permeabilities. c) Surface seawater fractions at different fault permeabilities along the ABF. d) 3D clip of a hydraulic-thermal simulation along the ABF for a 15 m wide fault, showing temperature, pore water velocity magnitude (represented by arrows), and isotherms (every 50°C). Figures (e) and (f) present three hydraulic-thermal numerical simulations at various fault widths (15, 45, and 105 m), with graphs illustrating surface values along the ABF. e) Temperature distribution along the ABF. f) Water density along the ABF. Note the highest temperature and lowest density were observed 3 km onshore.

317

Figure 5. Sensitivity analysis of simulation Case I showing the increase in fault zone permeability until the surface temperature of La Jolla beach (~100 °C) is reproduced. The reddish colors represent a high fraction of seawater, while the bluish colors indicate a low or negligible fraction.

318

3.2 Case II: seafloor sediment layer (synthetic case)

In order to accurately simulate the thermal anomaly at La Jolla beach, we introduced a thin layer of seafloor sediment in our modeling approach to restrict the infiltration of seawater along the ABF (Figure 6b). Our 2D cross-sectional simulations along the ABF (Figure 6) show that the seafloor sediment layer ($k = 10^{-18} \text{ m}^2$) and sediments intersected by the ABF ($k = 9 \times 10^{-16} - 4.5 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2$) effectively limits the infiltration of seawater, although not entirely. This synthetic case, Case II, successfully reproduces the observed location of the coastal geothermal system at La Jolla beach, which is a notable achievement.

As shown in Figure 6b, the infiltration of seawater through the ABF acts as a barrier, impeding the circulation of meteoric water beyond the coastline. The circulation depth of both fluids gives rise to an upflow zone of mixed thermal water beneath La Jolla beach, characterized by a pore water velocity of approximately $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. This process facilitates heat transfer from the rocks to the surface, resulting in a surface discharge water temperature of approximately ~ 100 °C and a seawater fraction of approximately $\sim 40\%$ (Figure 6b).

Furthermore, we conducted simulations for three different fault widths (15, 45, and 105 m) and observed that reducing the fault's permeability as the width increases is crucial for accurately reproducing a surface temperature of approximately ~ 100 °C and a seawater fraction ranging from $\sim 20\%$ to 80% (Figure 6c and 5d). Interestingly, the length and shape of the thermal anomaly along the ABF, spanning approximately 3 km, remain comparable for all three simulated fault widths. Our simulation results also reveal that the upflow of mixed thermal water exhibits a lower density (960 kg m^{-3}) and viscosity (0.28 cP) than the infiltrated seawater ($\sim 1025 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and 1.4 cP) and meteoric water ($\sim 1000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and 1.2 cP), respectively (Figure 6e and 5f). This phenomenon can be attributed to the decrease in density and viscosity as the fluid temperature increases.

Simulation Case II reveal that a thin seafloor sediment layer plays a crucial role in reducing seawater infiltration, which is necessary to replicate the temperature and location of the La Jolla beach coastal geothermal system. However, we also found that an unusually long thermal anomaly is produced at the surface (~ 3 km). To address this issue, we conducted additional numerical simulations (Case III), which will be discussed in the following subchapter.

Figure 6. Hydraulic–thermal numerical simulations and analysis from Case II. a) Topography and bathymetry section along the ABF. The green layer represents the 50 m seafloor sediment layer, and the dotted black vertical line (~ at 12 km) indicates the location of La Jolla beach along the fault profile. b) 3D clip of a hydraulic–thermal simulation for a fault width of 15 m, displaying temperature, pore water velocity magnitude (represented by arrows), and isotherms

(every 50°C). Figures (c), (d), (e) and (f) present three hydraulic-thermal numerical simulations at various fault widths (15, 45, and 105 m), with graphs illustrating surface values along the ABF. c) Temperature distribution. d) Seawater fraction distribution. e) Water density distribution. f) Water viscosity. It is important to note that the highest temperature, lowest density, and viscosity occur at the coastal zone.

348

349 3.3 Case III: Crystalline basement and sedimentary basin

350 In order to gain a comprehensive understanding of coastal geothermal systems and
351 accurately replicate the temperature, location, and length of the La Jolla Beach geothermal system,
352 we conducted simulations that incorporated the topography of the crystalline basement and the
353 distribution of sediments in the basins of Bahia Todos Santos and the Maneadero valley (Figure
354 7a). The results of these simulations are presented in Figure 7, which provides insights into various
355 characteristics of thermal water both at the surface and in depth.

356 Figure 7b depicts how hydrostatic pressure gradients, originating from the mountainous
357 zone and the Pacific Ocean, drive the flow of meteoric and seawater through the ABF at
358 considerable depths. To create upflow zones with surface thermal anomalies, water velocity along
359 regional faults must exceed 10^{-7} m s^{-1} (López & Smith, 1995; Wanner et al., 2020; Alt-Epping et
360 al., 2021, 2022). In our simulations, water velocity in our simulations ranges from 4×10^{-20} to $4 \times$
361 10^{-5} m s^{-1} , with the highest velocities occurring in the upflow zone along the ABF plane beneath
362 La Jolla beach, where high-temperature water circulates.

363 Our study reveals that the width of the fault zone has a limited influence on the location,
364 temperature, and amplitude of the thermal anomaly observed at the surface. Across all fault widths
365 considered, our simulations consistently reproduce a thermal anomaly in the coastal zone with a
366 surface temperature of approximately 100 °C and an amplitude spanning around 1 km (Figure 7c).
367 However, the width of the fault zone does play a role in determining the amount of water flux that
368 flows through it.

369 Specifically, when the fault width is 15 m, the total water flux discharged along the ABF
370 reach up to 720 kg d⁻¹. In comparison, for fault widths of 45 and 105 m, the total water flux
371 increases to 1119 and 1434 kg d⁻¹, respectively (Figure 7d). Furthermore, the water flux in the
372 discharge zones is well-correlated with the low hydrostatic pressure, which increases as the

373 hydrostatic pressure decreases (Figure 7d,e). The lowest shallow hydrostatic pressure along the
374 ABF is in the coastal zone, facilitating the upflow of thermal water (Figure 7e).

375 Seawater density plays a crucial role in preventing the circulation of meteoric water beyond
376 the coastline, acting as a natural barrier. The seawater mixing fraction varies between 10% and
377 35% in the three simulations (Figure 7f). Furthermore, the distribution of sediment in the
378 Maneadero valley basin and Bahia Todos Santos influences the shape of the 100°C isotherm,
379 guiding the flow of thermal water towards the coast (Figure 7b). Additionally, our simulations
380 reveal the presence of a convection cell beneath the Pacific Ocean along the ABF plane,
381 characterized by a seawater fraction ranging from 50 to 80%. This convection cell arises from the
382 density contrast between seawater and meteoric water, as well as the lateral infiltration of meteoric
383 water from the Punta Banda peninsula (Electronic Appendix Figure S1).

384 Seawater viscosity is indeed an important factor to consider in coastal geothermal systems,
385 although its influence is relatively less significant compared to density. This is because viscosity
386 tends to decrease more rapidly than density with increasing temperature. In our simulations, we
387 observe that seawater infiltrating into the ABF initially has a maximum viscosity of around 1.6 cP,
388 which progressively decreases to a minimum of 0.1 cP within the system. In contrast, the thermal
389 water at the surface exhibits a viscosity of approximately 0.3 cP (Figure 7g). These results indicate
390 that the viscosity value can decrease by up to 90% from its initial value. On the other hand, the
391 maximum density of seawater is approximately 1030 kg m^{-3} , which can decrease to a minimum of
392 820 kg m^{-3} within the system. Comparatively, the thermal water at the surface has a density of
393 about 957 kg m^{-3} , resulting in a reduction of density of up to 20%. Therefore, in the context of
394 coastal geothermal systems, the density of seawater plays a more significant role than viscosity in
395 determining the behavior and distribution of thermal anomalies, acting as a crucial factor in
396 regulating the extent of meteoric water circulation along the coast.

397 All simulations were run for up to 1,000,000 years to ensure a steady state was reached. In
398 the Electronic Appendix (Figure S2), we present the evolution of various properties of the thermal
399 anomaly, such as temperature, seawater fraction, density, and viscosity, on the surface for a 15-
400 meter-wide fault at 12 different simulation times. We observed an anomaly of approximately 40°C
401 generated under the Pacific Ocean, located between km 8 and 10, after 10,000 years. As time
402 progresses, the temperature of the anomaly gradually increases and moves towards the coastal
403 zone due to the infiltration of seawater through the ABF, which moves the rising zone of hot water.

404 After 500,000 years, the simulations reached a steady state, with the anomaly remaining at a
 405 temperature of around 100 °C on the coastal zone. This observation suggests that the age of the
 406 coastal amagmatic geothermal system at La Jolla beach could be as old as 1,000,000 years,
 407 assuming that the fault permeability and sediment conditions have remained similar to the present
 408 day. This age aligns well with the estimated tectonic activation of the ABF approximately 1.3
 409 million years ago.

Figure 7. Hydraulic–thermal numerical simulations resulted from Case III. a) Topography and bathymetry section along the ABF, also showing the topography of the crystalline basement and the distribution of sediments. The dotted black vertical line (~ at 12 km) represents the location of La Jolla beach along of the fault profile. d) Clip in 3D of a hydraulic–thermal simulation along of the ABF for a fault width of 15 m. Temperature, pore water velocity magnitude (arrows), and isotherms (every 50 °C) are shown. Figures c to g represents three hydraulic–thermal numerical simulations under different fault widths (15, 45, and 105 m), the graphs show surface values along the ABF. c) Temperature distribution. d) Seawater fractions. e) Viscosity along the ABF plane, note the lower viscosity values at La Jolla beach. f) Water flux discharge and g) hydrostatic pressure along the ABF. Note the lowest hydrostatic pressure occurred at the coastal zone.

410

411 4.1 Water infiltration and discharge

412 The study area has a subtropical arid climate with an annual precipitation averaging 275
413 mm annually. The quantification of meteoric water infiltration on the upper boundary of the 3D
414 hydraulic–thermal simulations (4.2–12.4 mm yr⁻¹) suggests that only 1.9–7.0% of the annual
415 precipitation is generated in the three simulation cases (Table 2). However, it is worth noting that
416 that in all three simulation cases, a greater proportion (54–85%) of meteoric water infiltrates than
417 seawater (15–46%). Additionally, the percentage of water infiltrating through the fault zone
418 (77–98%) is higher than that of the host rock (2–23%), likely due to the high permeability of the
419 fault zone (Table 2). Despite being smaller than the infiltration along the fault plane (77–85%),
420 the infiltration through the host rock (15–23%) plays a significant role in controlling the flow
421 direction and potential energy to drive fluids in the upper crust, as demonstrated by Simulation
422 Case III.

423 On the other hand, the results of the simulations also reveal a thermal anomaly of ≥ 50 °C,
424 with a water discharge range of 0.2 to 1.1 L s⁻¹. The water flow discharge increases with an increase
425 in fault width. In Case III, which simulates the thermal anomaly at La Jolla beach and reproduces
426 its location, temperature, and size, the thermal water discharge ranges from 0.7 to 1.1 L s⁻¹ over an
427 area of 0.112 km² (Figure 8a). The simulated size and temperature of the thermal anomaly is
428 similar to that recorded in the study area (500 m long and 94 °C) as well as the mixing fraction
429 with seawater (10–40%).

430 The water circulation driven by hydraulic heads from the mountainous zone and Pacific
431 Ocean occurs at high depth, where heat is transported towards the coastal zone (e.g., 6 km, Figure
432 8b). This effect produces two cold thermal anomalies beneath areas with a higher head gradient
433 (Figure 8b). Heat transport from these areas creates a thermal anomaly with high temperatures
434 beneath zones with a low hydraulic gradient, such as the coastal zone. It is worth noting that the
435 size of the deep thermal anomaly is longer and wider than that of the surface (Figure 8a,b).
436 Furthermore, the fluid pressure along the thermal water upflow pathway is found to be lowest
437 along the ABF. Specifically, at a depth of 6 km beneath La Jolla Beach, the simulated fluid pressure
438 is 58 MPa, whereas in the Pacific Ocean and the mountainous zone, the pressure reaches up to 61
439 MPa (Figure 8c). This effect is because the thermal water is ascending at high temperature and
440 velocity compare with the surrounding in the hostrock.

441 Previous studies investigating fault-hosted orogenic amagmatic geothermal systems have
442 utilized thermal-hydraulic simulations that incorporate the tectonic and topographic characteristics
443 of their respective study areas. These simulations have successfully reproduced the temperature
444 and spatial distribution of thermal anomalies at the surface by considering fault permeabilities and
445 thicknesses in the range of 10^{-15} – 10^{-14} m² and 100–300 m, respectively and special boundary
446 conditions. However, some of these simulations have produced thermal anomalies with extreme
447 sizes at the surface. For example, along the Têt fault in the Eastern Pyrénées, France, thermal
448 anomalies on valley floors can reach lengths of up to ~8 km (Taillefer et al., 2018). This
449 discrepancy in size may be attributed to the thermal boundary condition applied to the surface of
450 the model, where a higher heat transfer coefficient results in an increased heat flow in those areas.
451 As a result, when the hot deep fluid reaches the surface, it encounters regions with high heat flow,
452 leading to a significant expansion of the thermal anomaly.

453 Another example is seen in the Grimsel Mountain Pass in the Swiss Alps, where
454 simulations reproduce a thermal anomaly approximately 0.5 km in length by introducing a vertical
455 conduit of 100 × 100 m high permeability (10^{-13} m²) along the fault plane (Wanner et al., 2019;
456 Alt-Epping et al., 2022). However, it is important to note that this configuration may not apply to
457 all amagmatic geothermal systems worldwide. In our simulation, we were able to achieve a coastal
458 thermal anomaly of approximately ~0.5 km in length without increasing the heat flux at the surface
459 in the geothermal zone or incorporating a permeable vertical conduit.

460

Table 2

Quantification of infiltration of seawater and meteoric water in the upper boundary of the model for the three cases of hydraulic–thermal simulations at different fault widths. The quantification of thermal water exfiltration at a temperature equal to or greater than 50 °C ($L s^{-1}$) is also shown as well as the total amount of water infiltrated through the fault and hostrock (%).

Fault width (m)	15	45	105
CASE III			
Seawater ($mm yr^{-1}$)	0.9	1.2	1.4
Meteoric water ($mm yr^{-1}$)	4.2	4.6	8.0
Seawater infiltration (%)	18	21	15
Meteoric water (%)	82	79	85
Infiltrated via fault (%)	77	84	85
Infiltrated via hostrock (%)	23	16	15
Discharge $\geq 50^{\circ}C$ ($L s^{-1}$)	0.7	0.9	1.1
CASE II			
Seawater ($mm yr^{-1}$)	3.6	3.7	3.7
Meteoric water ($mm yr^{-1}$)	6.8	7.9	10.6
Seawater infiltration (%)	34	32	26
Meteoric water (%)	66	68	74
Infiltrated via fault (%)	97	87	98
Infiltrated via hostrock (%)	3	13	2
Discharge $\geq 50^{\circ}C$ ($L s^{-1}$)	1.2	1.2	1.3
CASE I			
Seawater ($mm yr^{-1}$)	6.3	5.3	7.1
Meteoric water ($mm yr^{-1}$)	7.3	8.2	12.4
Seawater infiltration (%)	46	39	36
Meteoric water (%)	54	61	64
Infiltrated via fault (%)	97	97	98
Infiltrated via hostrock (%)	3	3	2
Discharge $\geq 50^{\circ}C$ ($L s^{-1}$)	0.2	0.2	0.3

Figure 8. Shape and size of the thermal anomaly observed at La Jolla Beach. a) The shallow thermal anomaly at a depth of 30 m is depicted, highlighting its location in the coastal zone. b) Temperature distribution at a depth of 6 km, providing insights into the extent of the thermal anomaly distribution in the subsurface. c) Low fluid pressure zone at 6 km depth beneath the coastal zone, which is related to the thermal water upflow and is depicted by the lowest fluid pressure along the ABF.

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467

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469

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Figure S1. 3D clip of Simulation Case III, showing a hydraulic-thermal simulation perpendicular to the ABF with a fault width of 15 m. The clip demonstrates the important role of the Punta Banda Peninsula in water flow, as there is a decrease in the seawater fraction along the ABF plane.

Figure S2. Time evolution from 10 to 1,000,000 years of different fluid properties of simulation Case III with a fault width of 15 m and $k = 6.5 \times 10^{-14}$. The position of the thermal anomaly remains in the coastal zone since the simulated time of 250,000 years.

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